

Antibody Characterization Report for PLC-gamma-2

YCharOS Antibody Characterization Report

Author(s): Riham Ayoubi¹, Maryam Fotouhi^{1,†}, Joel Ryan^{2,†}, Wolfgang Reintsch³, Thomas M. Durcan³, Claire Brown², Peter S. McPherson¹ and Carl Laflamme^{1*}

† Authors contributed equally

¹ Department of Neurology and Neurosurgery, Structural Genomics Consortium, The Montreal Neurological Institute, McGill University, Montreal, Quebec, Canada

² Advanced BioImaging Facility (ABIF), McGill University, Montreal, Canada

³ The Neuro's Early Drug Discovery Unit (EDDU), Structural Genomics Consortium, Montreal

* Corresponding author: carl.laflamme@mcgill.ca

Target:

Recommended protein name: 1-phosphatidylinositol 4,5-bisphosphate phosphodiesterase gamma-2

Short protein name: PLC-gamma-2

Alternative protein name: Phosphoinositide phospholipase C-gamma-2, Phospholipase C-IV, Phospholipase C-gamma-2

Gene name: *PLCG2*

Uniprot: P16885

We are a third-party organization with the mission to characterize commercial antibodies for all human protein through open science [1]. In this study, we characterized eleven PLC-gamma-2 commercial antibodies for Western Blot, immunoprecipitation, and immunofluorescence using a standardized experimental protocol [2] based on comparing read-outs in knockout cell lines and isogenic parental controls. We identified many well-performing antibodies and encourage readers to use this report as a guide to select the most appropriate antibody for their specific needs. An HAP1 *PLCG2* KO line is available at Horizon discovery and was used in this study. Expression of PLC-gamma-2 protein in HAP1 is adequate as determined by searching DepMap [3].

The authors do not provide an assessment of the quality of the tested antibodies as their respective performances are limited to our finite experimental conditions. The readers should interpret the present findings based on their own scientific expertise. The authors acknowledge that an antibody that demonstrates specificity in the stated test conditions can be suboptimal in a different experimental format or in cell lines that differ from those directly tested here.

Table 1: Summary of the cell lines used

Institution	Catalog number	RRID (Cellosaurus)	Cell line	Genotype
Horizon Discovery	C631	CVCL_Y019	HAP1	WT
Horizon Discovery	HZGHC003391c005	CVCL_TE38	HAP1	<i>PLCG2</i> KO
Abcam	ab255451	CVCL_0291	HCT116	WT
Abcam	ab271147	CVCL_0006	THP-1	WT

Table 2: Summary of the PLC-gamma-2 antibodies tested

Company	Catalog number	Lot number	RRID (Antibody Registry)	Clonality	Clone ID	Host	Concentration ($\mu\text{g}/\mu\text{l}$)	Vendors recommended applications
Abcam	ab109267**	GR498527	AB_10888119	recombinant-mono	EPR1403	rabbit	1.32	Wb
Abcam	ab133522**	GR962819	AB_2927390	recombinant-mono	EPR5914-34	rabbit	0.63	Wb
Bio-Techne	MAB3716*	XXN0319021	AB_2163529	monoclonal	346404	mouse	0.50	Wb,IF
Bio-Techne	NBP2-52536*	141225	AB_2927391	monoclonal	2D9E8	mouse	1.00	Wb,IF
Cell Signaling Technology	3872	5	AB_2299586	polyclonal	-	rabbit	0.12	Wb,IP
Cell Signaling Technology	34264**	1	AB_2927393	recombinant-mono	E7L6G	rabbit	0.39	Wb
Cell Signaling Technology	55512**	1	AB_2799488	recombinant-mono	E5U4T	rabbit	0.05	Wb,IP,IF
GeneTex	GTX111178	40058	AB_1951276	polyclonal	-	rabbit	0.66	Wb,IF
GeneTex	GTX111293	43334	AB_1951274	polyclonal	-	rabbit	0.75	Wb
Thermo Fisher Scientific	MA5-35670**	XH3670294	AB_2849570	recombinant-mono	ARC1176	rabbit	0.73	Wb
Thermo Fisher Scientific	MA5-38600*	XH3669859	AB_2898512	monoclonal	2D9E8	mouse	1.00	Wb,IF

Wb=Western blot, IP= immunoprecipitation, IF=immunofluorescence, *=monoclonal antibody, **=recombinant antibody

Materials and methods

Antibodies

All tested PLC-gamma-2 antibodies are listed in Table 2. Peroxidase-conjugated goat anti-mouse and anti-rabbit are from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number 62-6520 and 65-6120). Alexa-555-conjugated goat anti-mouse and anti-rabbit secondary antibodies are from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number A21424 and A21429).

Cell culture

Cells were cultured in DMEM high glucose (GE Healthcare cat. number SH30081.01) containing 10% fetal bovine serum (Wisent, cat. number 080450), 2 mM L-glutamate (Wisent cat. number 609065, 100 IU penicillin and 100 µg/ml streptomycin (Wisent cat. number 450201).

THP-1 WT were treated with 200 ng/ml of phorbol 12-myristate 13-acetate (PMA) (Abcam, cat. number ab147465) for 2 days. 200 ng/ml of PMA were added in fresh media for both day 1 and day 2 [4].

Antibody screening by Western Blot

Western Blots were performed as described in our standard operating procedure [5]. HAP1 WT and *PLCG2* KO (listed in Table 1) were collected in RIPA buffer (25mM Tris-HCl pH 7.6, 150mM NaCl, 1% NP-40, 1% sodium deoxycholate, 0.1% SDS) supplemented with 1x protease inhibitor cocktail mix (MilliporeSigma, cat. number 78429). Lysates were sonicated briefly and incubated 30 min on ice. Lysates were spun at ~110,000xg for 15 min at 4°C and equal protein aliquots of the supernatants were analyzed by SDS-PAGE and Western Blot. HiMark™ Pre-stained Protein Standard from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number LC5699) was used.

Western Blots were performed with precast midi 3-8% Tris-Acetate polyacrylamide gels from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number WG1601BOX) ran with Tris-Acetate SDS buffer (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number LA0041), loaded in LDS sample buffer (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number NP0008) with 1x sample reducing agent (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number NP0009) and transferred on nitrocellulose membranes. Proteins on the blots were visualized with Ponceau staining which is scanned to show together with individual Western Blot. Blots were blocked with 5% milk for 1 hr, and antibodies were incubated O/N at 4°C with 5% milk in TBS with 0,1% Tween 20 (TBST) from Cell Signaling (cat. number 9997). Following three washes with TBST, the peroxidase conjugated secondary antibody was incubated at a dilution

of ~0.2 µg/ml in TBST with 5% milk for 1 hr at room temperature followed by three washes with TBST. Membranes are incubated with Pierce ECL from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number 32106) prior to detection with the iBright™ CL1500 Imaging System from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number A44240).

Antibody screening by immunoprecipitation

Immunoprecipitation was performed as described in our standard operating procedure [6]. Antibody-bead conjugates were prepared by adding 2 µg or 20 µl of antibody at an unknown concentration to 500 µl of Pierce IP Lysis Buffer from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number 87788) in a microcentrifuge tube, together with with 30µl of Dynabeads protein A- (for rabbit antibodies) or protein G- (for mouse antibodies) from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number 10002D and 10004D, respectively). Tubes were rocked for ~1 hr at 4°C followed by several washes to remove unbound antibodies.

HAP1 WT were collected in Pierce IP buffer (25 mM Tris-HCl pH 7.4, 150 mM NaCl, 1 mM EDTA, 1% NP-40 and 5% glycerol) supplemented with protease inhibitor. Lysates are rocked 30 min at 4°C and spun at 110,000xg for 15 min at 4°C. 0.5 ml aliquots at 2.0 mg/ml of lysate were incubated with an antibody-bead conjugate for ~1 hr at 4°C. The unbound fractions were collected, and beads were subsequently washed three times with 1.0 ml of IP lysis buffer and processed for SDS-PAGE and Western Blot on precast midi 3-8% Tris-Acetate polyacrylamide gels from Thermo Fisher Scientific.

Antibody screening by immunofluorescence

Immunofluorescence was performed as described in our standard operating procedure [7]. HAP1 WT and *PLCG2* KO were labelled with a green and a far-red fluorescence dye, respectively. The fluorescent dyes used are from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number C2925 and C34565). WT and KO cells were plated in a 96-well plate with optically clear flat-bottom. (Perkin Elmer, cat. number 6055300) as a mosaic and incubated for 24 hrs in a cell culture incubator. Cells were fixed in 4% PFA (in PBS) for 15 min at room temperature and then washed 3 times with PBS. Cells were permeabilized in PBS with 0,1% Triton X-100 for 10 min at room temperature and blocked with PBS with 5% BSA, 5% goat serum and 0.01% Triton X-100 for 30 min at room temperature. Cells were incubated with IF buffer (PBS, 5% BSA, 0,01% Triton X-100) containing the primary PLC-gamma-2 antibodies O/N at 4°C. Cells were then washed 3 × 10 min with IF buffer and incubated with corresponding Alexa Fluor 555-conjugated

secondary antibodies in IF buffer at a dilution of 1.0 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ for 1 hr at room temperature with DAPI. Cells were washed 3×10 min with IF buffer and once with PBS.

Images were acquired on an ImageXpress micro widefield high-content microscopy system (Molecular Devices), using a 20x NA 0.95 water immersion objective and scientific CMOS cameras, equipped with 395, 475, 555 and 635 nm solid state LED lights (lumencor Aura III light engine) and bandpass filters to excite DAPI, Cellmask Green, Alexa568 and Cellmask Red, respectively. Images had pixel sizes of 0.68 x 0.68 microns, and a z-interval of 4 microns. For analysis and visualization, shading correction (shade only) was carried out for all images. Then, maximum intensity projections were generated using 3 z-slices. Segmentation was carried out separately on maximum intensity projections of Cellmask channels using CellPose 1.0, and masks were used to generate outlines and for intensity quantification. Figures were assembled with Adobe Illustrator.

Figure 1: PLC-gamma-2 antibody screening by Western Blot

Figure 2: PLC-gamma-2 antibody screening by immunoprecipitation

Figure 3: PLC-gamma-2 antibody screening antibody screening by immunofluorescence (1/2)

Figure 3: PLC-gamma-2 antibody screening antibody screening by immunofluorescence (2/2)

Figure 1: PLC-gamma-2 antibody screening by Western Blot.

A) Lysates of HAP1 WT and *PLCG2* KO were prepared, and 50 µg of protein were processed for Western Blot with the indicated PLC-gamma-2 antibodies. The Ponceau stained transfers of each blot are shown. All antibodies were tested at a dilution of 1/500. Predicted band size: 148 kDa. B) Lysates of HAP1 (WT and *PLCG2* KO), HCT116 WT and THP-1 WT, untreated (UT) or treated with PMA were processed as in A). *=monoclonal antibody, **=recombinant antibody

Figure 2: PLC-gamma-2 antibody screening by immunoprecipitation.

HAP1 lysates were prepared, and immunoprecipitation was performed using 2.0 µg of the indicated PLC-gamma-2 antibodies pre-coupled to Dynabeads protein G or protein A. Samples were washed and processed for Western Blot with the indicated PLC-gamma-2 antibody. For Western Blot, 55512** was used at 1/500. The Ponceau stained transfers of each blot are shown. SM=4% starting material; UB=4% unbound fraction; IP=immunoprecipitate. *=monoclonal antibody, **=recombinant antibody, ?=undetermined band

Figure 3: PLC-gamma-2 antibody screening by immunofluorescence.

HAP1 WT and *PLCG2* KO cells were labelled with a green or a far-red fluorescent dye, respectively. WT and KO cells were mixed and plated to a 1:1 ratio in a 96-well plate with optically clear flat-bottom. Cells were stained with the indicated PLC-gamma-2 antibodies and with the corresponding Alexa-fluor 555 coupled secondary antibody including DAPI. Acquisition of the blue (nucleus-DAPI), green (identification of WT cells), red (antibody staining) and far-red (identification of KO cells) channels was performed. Representative images of the blue and red (grayscale) channels are shown. WT and KO cells are outlined with green and magenta dashed line, respectively. Antibody were tested at 1.0 µg/ml. Bars = 10 µm. *=monoclonal antibody, **=recombinant antibody

References

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